

Research Article

An Observational Analytical Study of the Fatigue Index in Young Adult with Reference to Different Mizaj

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Abstract

Fatigue is one of the most common symptoms in clinical medicine. It is a prominent manifestation of a number of systemic, neurologic, and psychiatric syndromes, although a precise cause will not be identified in a substantial minority of patients. Fatigue refers to the subjective human experience of physical and mental weariness, sluggishness, low energy, and exhaustion.^[1] Fatigue is typically described as extreme and persistent tiredness, weakness, or exhaustion, whether mental, physical, or both. In many cases, fatigue doesn't have a clear physical cause and can arise as a result of illness or simply from exertion, inadequate rest, or an inadequate diet. Therefore, it's best to think of fatigue as a spectrum, ranging from mild complaints that are frequently seen in the community to severe, disabling fatigue that can have significant social and economic consequences.^[2] The concept of *Mizaj* in the Unani system of medicine is a vast area of research. *Mizaj* theory finds its roots in the ancient four *Humors* theory. This medical theory was systematized and developed by the Greek physician *Buqrat* (Hippocrates, 460-370 BC). He believed that the body, and diagnosis caused certain human moods, emotions, and behaviours and line of management of any disease is based upon it. In this cross-sectional descriptive study to assess the *Mizaj* and fatigue severity, we used *Mizaj* assessment proforma based on classical literature and fatigue severity scale in apparently healthy individuals of different ages and both genders & this study was carried out in students of Ayurvedic and Unani tibbia College & Hospital, Karol Bagh New Delhi.

Keywords: Fatigue, *Mizaj*, Fatigue severity scale (FSS) and Young Adult.

Introduction

Unani Medicine, also known as Greco-Arab medicine, is an ancient medical system that originated from Greece. It is based on the teachings of Greek physician Hippocrates and Roman physician Galen. The system was then developed into an elaborate medical system by Arab and Persian physicians such as *Rhazes*, *Avicenna* (IbnSena), *Al-Zahrawi*, and *Ibn Nafis*^[1]. The Unani system describes seven essential components of the body called *Umoor-e-Tabiya*. These include *Arkanor* elements (comprising earth, water, air, and fire as different states of matter and the building blocks of everything in the universe), *Mizaj* (temperament), *Akhlat* (Humors), *Aza* (organs), *Arwaah* (life, spirit or vital breath), *Quwa* (energy), and *Afaal* (action).

The framework of this system is based on the concept of *Mizaj* (temperament) and *Akhlat* (Humors). The Unani system provides insights into human personalities by classifying them into four different *Mizaj* (temperaments) based on the dominance of body fluids (Humors). Drugs and diseases are also classified as having different *Mizaj* according to the four *Humors* in treatment^[2]. *Mizaj* is one of the basic and fundamental concepts of the Unani system of medicine, which is a new median (*kaifiyat*) produced by the composition of different elements (*anasir*).

Mizaj is the discriminating feature upon which human health, disease, diagnosis, and treatment are based. According to nature, *Mizaj* is divided into four categories known as *Damvi* (Sanguine), *Balghami* (Phlegmatic), *Safrawi* (Choleretic), and *Saudawi* (Melancholic). According to *IbnNafis*, the literal meaning of *Mizaj* is 'intermixture', which originated from the Arabic word *Imtizaj*, meaning intermixture^[3].

Temperament is a quality that emerges from the mutual interaction and interspersion of the four contrary primary qualities, namely earth, water, air, and fire, residing within the imponderable elements. The *Mizaj*, as defined by *Majoosi*, encompasses all kinds of bodies found in the ever-changing world that are

formed from these four elements. After mixing invarious or uniform quantities and under the requirements of the body, one or two qualities become dominant over the body, resulting in *Mizaj*. *Hippocrates*, the Unani physician, set forth the doctrine of body fluids in his book "*Human Nature*," which states that the human body contains four major kinds of *Humors* or *Akhlat*, blood (*Dam*), phlegm (*Balgham*), yellow bile (*Safra*), and black bile (*Sauda*). The accurate proportion and mixing of these *Humors* in quantity and quality constitute health, while an inaccurate proportion and irregular distribution lead to disease. To evaluate a person's normal body function, it is necessary to assess their respective *Mizaj* or *Taskhees-e-Mizaj* based on physiological, morphological, and psychological features. *Ajnas-e-Ashra* describes different *Mizaj* (Temperament) of the body, including *Malmus* (Tactus), *Lahamwa Shaham* (Flesh and Fat), *Shaar* (Hair), *Laun-e-Badan* (Body Complexion), *Haiyat-e-Aza* (Stature/Physique), *Kaifiyat-e-Infial* (Quality of Passiveness of Organ), *Naumwa Yaqzah* (Sleep and Wakefulness), *Afaal-e-Azaa* (State of Organs Function), *Fuzlaat-e-Badan* (Body Excretion), and *Infialat-e-Nafsaaniyah* (Psychic Reaction). Each organ of the human body has its unique *Mizaj*, which, when combined, results in the individual's temperament. The treatment is determined based on the patient's temperament and follows a sequential approach: *Ilaj BilT adabeerwa Agziya* (Regimental/Diet-Therapy), *Ilaj Bil Dawa* (Pharmaco-Therapy), and *Ilaj Bil Yad* (Surgical Intervention). Surgical intervention is the final option when all other therapies fail to provide the desired results^{[4][5]}. In Unani medicine, fatigue is known as *Iya* (*Takaan*). This condition is recognized as a general feeling of tiredness and lack of energy, often accompanied by physical and mental exhaustion. There are three types of *Iya*: *quruhi*, *tamaddudi*, and *warmi*.

Iya e Quroohi: refers to a condition characterized by "*Iya*" fatigue that feels like a wound or soreness in the skin. This sensation

is accompanied by a tingling feeling known as “*Qashareera*” The condition is caused by *Akhlat e raddiya* and *mawad e fasida* which are spoiled substances. When the substances enter the veins, they can disrupt the balance of good blood, potentially causing harm. However, nature typically directs these substances towards the skin in a purer form, minimizing their irritative effects. The most common harm caused by these spoiled substances is the tingling sensation^{[7][9]}.

If these substances manage to enter the veins due to movement or agitation, they can cause tingling, and with increased agitation, tremors may occur. The fermentation and ripening of these spoiled substances require time, and until they are eliminated, they remain harmful and not useful to the body. These substances, referred to as *Akhlat e Khamma* (raw Humors), can sometimes enter specific veins and persist in their raw state within the muscles.

Iya e Tamaddudi: is a condition where a person experiences a sensation as if their body has been crushed, accompanied by feelings of heat and tension. This condition makes movement unpleasant for the individual, to the extent that they may not even want to move their finger, particularly when the fatigue is due to excessive work. The underlying cause of *Iya e Tamaddudi* is waste that remains within the muscle structure. However, these wastes are not always inherently harmful or painful. The primary culprit behind this condition is referred to as “*reeh*”.

Iya e Maddi and *Iya e Tamaddudi* are two distinct conditions differentiated by their sensations of heaviness and lightness, respectively. *Iya e Maddi* is characterized by a feeling of heaviness, while *Iya e Tamaddudi* is associated with a sensation of lightness. Fatigue from “*Iya e Maddi*” can sometimes be attributed to lack of sleep, and adequate rest often alleviates this type of fatigue.

Iya e Warmi: represents a state where the body's temperature rises above its normal level. This condition is characterized by the swelling of organs, which not only increase in

size but also change in colour, resembling inflamed tissues. Such swollen organs become sensitive to touch and movement, and a noticeable tension is felt within them. The affected organs often take on a reddish, shiny appearance due to this heightened tension, causing the skin covering them to become tight and more luminous. It's worth noting that the symptoms of “*Iya e Warmi*” intensify when an individual stands or walks for extended periods, as highlighted by *Gailani*. On the other hand, *Iya e Qazofi* represents a different subtype of *Iya*. In this condition, individuals experience an unusual sensation of dryness and constipation throughout their body. The root cause of *Iya e Qazofi* can be attributed to excessive physical exertion, which leads to an overburdened heart, considered a heat-producing organ. Additionally, this condition can be precipitated by prolonged fasting, extreme fasting combined with frequent sexual activity, or *Istifragh*.^{[6][7][8][9]} Fatigue is one of the most common symptoms in clinical medicine. It is a prominent manifestation of a number of systemic, neurologic, and psychiatric syndromes, although a precise cause will not be identified in a substantial minority of patients. Fatigue refers to the subjective human experience of physical and mental weariness, sluggishness, low energy, and exhaustion. In the context of clinical medicine, fatigue is most typically and practically defined as difficulty initiating or maintaining voluntary mental or physical activity.

Nearly everyone who has ever been ill with a self-limited infection has experienced this near-universal symptom, and fatigue is usually brought to medical attention only when it is either of unclear cause, fails to remit, or the severity is out of proportion with what would be expected for the associated trigger.^{[10][11][12][13]}

Fatigue should be distinguished from muscle weakness, a reduction of neuromuscular power. Most patients complaining of fatigue are not truly weak when direct muscle power is tested. Fatigue is also distinct from somnolence, which refers to sleepiness in the

context of disturbed sleep-wake physiology and from dyspnoea on exertion, although patients may use the word fatigue to describe those symptoms. The task facing clinicians when a patient presents with fatigue is to identify the underlying cause and to develop a therapeutic alliance, the goal of which is to spare patients expensive and fruitless diagnostic workups and steer them toward effective therapy.^{[14][15]}

Fatigue is a commonly experienced condition, however, due to the different definitions of fatigue and the variety of survey instruments used in different studies, it is difficult to determine exact figures of its global burden. According to a large survey conducted by the National Institute of Mental Health on the U.S. general population, the point prevalence of fatigue was 6.7%, while the lifetime prevalence was 25%. In Europe and the United States, primary care clinics have reported that between 10% and 25% of patients surveyed endorsed symptoms of prolonged (present for >1 month) or chronic (present for >6 months) fatigue, but only a minority cited fatigue as the primary reason for seeking medical attention. In India, a community survey of women showed that 12% reported chronic fatigue.

Approach to the Patient:

To diagnose fatigue syndrome, a thorough medical history is necessary. It's important to distinguish fatigue from other symptoms and investigate potential triggers. A review of drug and alcohol use is also necessary. Fatigue impacts daily functioning and recovery, and a mental and neurological examination can help diagnose patients. Full power generation may be difficult, and breakaway weakness may or may not cause pain. Fatigable weakness usually indicates a neuromuscular transmission problem. Electromyography with nerve conduction studies can help diagnose muscle weakness. The overall physical examination should screen for signs of diseases related to the heart, lungs, cancer, organs, infections, malnutrition, hormonal imbalances, and connective tissue. A detailed

neuropsychiatric and mental status evaluation can identify the cause of fatigue in up to 75-80% of patients. Laboratory testing only helps identify the cause of chronic fatigue in about 5% of cases. A reasonable approach to screening includes a complete blood count, electrolytes, glucose, renal, liver, and thyroid function tests. Additional unfocused studies, such as whole-body imaging scans, are usually not necessary.^{[16][17]}

Aims and objectives:

Study of the fatigue index in various groups of persons of either gender with reference to different *Mizaj* (body type according to Unani system of medicine) to establish a relation between them.

Material and Method:

Study design: Prospective Observational Study.

Sample size: 100 samples selected.

Study Period: Study was conducted for a period of 3 months from 15 December to 15 March 2024.

Study criteria Inclusion criteria Healthy volunteer Person of either gender.

Person with age from 19 years Person with age up to 28 years.

Person not on medications or supplements.

Exclusion criteria

Smokers and tobacco users.

Women with Pregnancy.

Person with any muscle disorder.

Alcoholics.

Procedure:

This study was conducted in the Department of Physiology of Ayurvedic & Unani Tibbia College & Hospital in New Delhi, India. Institutional ethics committee (IEC) approved current study. The objective was to observe the correlation between *Mizaj* identification and fatigue severity in young adults. A total of 100 individuals between the ages of 19 to 28 were initially enrolled in the study after fulfilling the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Upon further screening, the final number of

individuals included in the study was 87. Prior to participating in the study, each individual was given an informed consent form which contained all the details of the study and required their signature. The identification of *Mizaj* was done using temperament assessment proforma generated by the Central Council for Research in Unani Medicine (CCRUM). The proforma helped to identify the individual's temperament, which is an important aspect of Unani medicine. To evaluate the level of fatigue in each individual, a fatigue severity scale (FSS) was

used. The FSS is a questionnaire designed to assess the level of fatigue in individuals. By using this questionnaire, the researchers were able to determine the severity of fatigue experienced by each participant.

Statistical Analysis: The SPSS-PC package (15 versions) was used for the statistical analysis of the data. Descriptive statistics such as means and standard deviations were calculated for the continuous variables. The criteria for statistical significance was $p < 0.05$.

Result

The study involved a random selection of 100 individuals to identify their *Mizaj* and determine the severity of fatigue using the Fatigue Severity Scale (FSS), according to specific inclusion and exclusion criteria. After screening, the study included a total of 87 individuals. Among the participants, the majority had *Damvi Mizaj*, with 30 individuals accounting for 34% of the total. *Balghami Mizaj* was found in 17 individuals (20%), *Safrawi Mizaj* in 21 individuals (24%), and *Saudawi Mizaj* in 19 individuals (22%). Overall, the study provides valuable insight into the prevalence of different *Mizaj* types and their association with fatigue severity.

Age	Damvi	Balghami	Safrawi	Saudawi
19-23	19	9	12	14
24-28	11	8	9	5
Total	30 (34%)	17 (20%)	21 (24%)	19 (22%)

Table1: Participants Data of Different *Mizaj* according to age groups

Figure1: participant's data regarding different *Mizaj* according to age group.

Figure 2: Volunteer data according to gender

Parameter	N	$\sum x$	Mean	$\sum x^2$	Std.Dev
Damvi	30	772	25.73	20902	5.9766
Balghami	17	464	27.29	12940	4.1498
Safrawi	21	476	22.67	11338	5.2377
Saudawi	19	466	24.53	11742	4.1682
Total	87	2178	25.055	56922	

Table 2: Statistical parameters according to different *Mizaj*.

Source	DF	SS	MS	F-Stat	P-Value
Between Groups	3	224.13	74.71	2.854	0.04211
Within Groups	83	2172.81	26.18		
Total	86	2396.94	27.87		

Table3: One-way ANOVA, The ANOVA as shown in table 3 result suggest FSS for different *Mizaj* groups differs significantly. (F= 2.854, P= 0.04211 at P < 0.05) and H₀ is rejected. **The f-ratio is 2.854. The p-value is 0.04211. The result is significant at p< .05.**

Figure 3: Mean and std. Deviation according to different *Mizaj*

According to the *Tukey HSD* test results in table 4, it was found that the Fatigue severity scale (FSS) score of *Balghami* (M=27.29, S.D. = 4.15) is significantly different from *Safrawi* (M=22.67, S.D.=5.24). However, *Damvi* (M=25.73, S.D.=5.98) is not significantly different from *Balghami* (M=27.29, S.D.=4.15), and *Damvi* (M=25.73, S.D.=5.98) is also not significantly different from *Safrawi* (M=22.67, S.D. = 5.24). Additionally, *Damvi* (M=25.73, S.D.= 5.98) is not significantly different from *Saudawi* (M=24.53, SD.=4.17), and *Balghami* (M=27.29, S.D.=4.15) is not significantly different from *Saudawi* (M=24.53, SD.=4.17). The mean difference was significant at the level of $P < 0.05$.

Pairwise Comparisons		HSD.05=4.1608	Q.05=3.7079	Q.01=4.5401
		HSD.01=5.0947		
T1: T2 Damvi:Balghami	M1=25.73 M2=27.29	1.56	Q=1.39(p=.75921)	
T1: T3 Damvi:Safrawi	M1=25.73 M3=22.67	3.07	Q=2.73(p=.22260)	
T1:T4 Damvi:Saudawi	M1=25.73 M4=24.53	1.21	Q=1.08(p=.87187)	
T2: T3 Balghami:Safrawi	M2=27.29 M3=22.67	4.63	Q=4.12(p=.02317)	
T2: T4 Balghami:Saudawi	M2=27.29 M4=24.53	2.77	Q=2.47(p=.30781)	
T3: T4 Safrawi:Saudawi	M3=22.67 M4=24.53	1.86	Q=1.66(p=.64623)	

Table 4: Pairwise comparison between different *Mizaj*

Figure 4: Graphical representation of pairwise comparison between different *Mizaj*.

Discussion

In this study, researchers examined the levels of fatigue indifferent groups of individuals using the Fatigue Severity Scale (FSS) questionnaire. The FSS scores were used to categorize participants into two groups: those with a total score of less than 36, indicating no significant fatigue, and those with a total score of 36 or more, indicating the presence of fatigue. This method is considered reliable for assessing fatigue. The study found that individuals with *Balghami Mizaj* had the highest average FSS score (27.29), while those with *Safrawi Mizaj* had the lowest average FSS score (22.67). According to classical Unani literature, there are four types of *Mizaj*, and it is believed that individuals with *Balghami Mizaj* are particularly susceptible to experiencing fatigue. The researchers also observed FSS scores across all four types of *Mizaj*, revealing that *Balghami Mizaj* had the highest mean score (27.29), followed by *Mizaje Damvi* (25.73), *Mizaje Saudawi* (24.53), and *Mizaj e Safrawi* (22.67). The differences among these groups were statistically significant ($P=0.042$ at the significance level $P<0.05$), indicating a strong

association between FSS scores and the variability of *Mizaj*. Furthermore, the study suggested that any type of *Mizaj* could predispose individuals to develop fatigue. Specifically, the study found a statistically significant mean difference ($P=0.023$ at the significance level $P<0.05$) between the *Balghami* and *Safrawi* groups. Further study with large sample size needs to be conducted to compare one *Mizaj* to the other *Mizaj* of the person.

Conclusion

The analysis of various observations shows that individuals with *Balghami Mizaj* tend to have the highest mean FSS (Fatigue Severity Scale) score, while those with *Safrawi Mizaj* tend to have the lowest. These findings support the experimental hypothesis of this research. The study clearly demonstrates a potential correlation between FSS and *Mizaj*. As a result, early diagnosis of this fatigue disorder is crucial in routine clinical practice, especially among individuals with *Balghami Mizaj*, to prevent potential negative outcomes.

Ethical Statement: Institutional ethics

committee (IEC) approved current study. Signed informed consent was collected from all participants, which contained all the details (Aim and purpose) of the study.

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Availability of Data and Material

The raw data and materials used to support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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Conflict of Interest– Authors declare none.

References:

1. https://www.nhp.gov.in/unani_mty
2. Iqra Hashmi, et al. Depression Symptomatology Correlation with *Mizaj* In Young College Students During The Lockdown. International Ayurvedic Medical Journal {online}2022{cited February2022}Available from:http://www.iamj.in/posts/images/upload/361_365.pdf
3. Ibn Sina AAHIA. Al Qanoon fit Tibb (Urdu Translation by Kantoori GH).New Delhi: Idara Kitab-us-Shifa, 2010.
4. Mustafii, Zyaat, Qadir HA, Najjar MA. Al-Mojam-al-Waseet. Deoband: Faisal Publication House, 2006.
5. Allamah kabiruddin, Ifada e Kabeer, National fine Printing press charakman, Hyderabad,8thedition,1970, 22.
6. Ahmad SI. Introduction to Al Ummorelil Tabiyaah CCRUM NewDelhi.1980:Ist Ed:16-17, 32-34,36- 37,75-82.
7. Ibn nafees B K ibn Ooz. “kulliyat-e-Nafeesi” Vol.2.(Urdu Translation) Hydrabad: (Deccan);1952:19, 59-74, 266-268, 269-272, 491.
8. Syed Kamaluddin Hussain Hamdani. Usool e tibb, qaumi council baray firoghurdujaban , New Delhi. 189-191.
9. Zakariya Razi (1991),‘Kitab-Al-Mansoori’, (urdutranslation) New Delh; CCRUM; YNM: 59-80
10. Viitasalo JT, Kyröläinen H, Bosco C, Alen M (1987) Effects of rapid weight reduction on force production and vertical jumping height. *Int J Sports Med* 4: 281–285.
11. Chevront SN, Carter R, Haymes EM, Sawka MN (2006) No effect of moderate hypohydration or hyperthermia on aerobic exercise performance. *Med Sci Sport Exerc* 38:1093–1097.
12. Judelson DA, Maresh CM, Farrell MJ, Yamamoto LM, Armstrong LE, et al.(2007) Effect of hydration state on strength, power, and resistance exercise performance. *Med Sci Sport Exerc*:1817–1824.
13. Laurent CM Jr, Meers MC, Robinson CA, Green JM (2007) Cross-validation of the 20-versus 30-s Wingate anaerobic test. *Eur J App Physiol*100: 645–651.
14. Jones LC, Cleary MA, Lopez RM, Zuri RE, Lopez R (2008) Active dehydration impairs upper and lower body an aerobic muscular power. *J Strength Cond Res* 22:455–463.
15. Kraft JA, Green JM, Bishop PA, Richardson MT, Negggers YH, et al. (2011) Effects of heat exposure and 3% dehydration achieved via hot water immersion on repeated cycle sprint performance. *J Strength Cond Res* 25:778–786.
16. Jameson, Fauci, Kasper, Hauser, Longo, Loscalzo. Harrison Internal Medicine edition 20th vol.1 pp132.
17. Kennedy, Adrian & Eparu, Dr. (2022). Prevalence of Fatigue in Indian Urban Population and its relation to nutritional factors. Available from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/358088814_Prevalence_of_Fatigue_in_India_n_Urban_Population_and_its_relation_to_nutritional_factors